

Mobile application			
Mobile psychoeducation	Performance	Volume and progression	Approximate total duration
<p>(1) introduction to the intervention program and mobile application,</p>	<p>introduction to the intervention program and use KaPi mobile application,</p>	<p>Introduction to the intervention program and KaPi mobile application 0.32 minute</p>	<p>0.32 minute</p>

<p>(2) introduction to mental health, (3) Psychological distress, (4) stress adaptation response, (5) coping self-efficacy,</p>	<p>(2) introduction to mental health, (3) Psychological distress, (4) stress adaptation response, (5) coping self-efficacy,</p>	<p>(2) introduction to mental health (0.39 minute) https://youtu.be/oZQMigrtlQM?feature=shared (3) Psychological distress (2.39 minute) https://youtu.be/HmB4exD2Qv4?feature=shared (4) stress adaptation response (2.55 minute) https://youtu.be/rhk_PuBhWL0?feature=shared (5) coping self-efficacy (0.34 minute)</p>	<p>Total duration 5,57 minute</p>

		https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gTUh5I2PCzA	
<p>(6) HIV and AIDS, (7) HIV transmission, (8) HIV/AIDS prevention, (9) HIV testing, (9) living with HIV</p> <p><small>Made with PosterMyWall.com</small></p>	<p>(6) HIV and AIDS, (7) HIV transmission, (8) HIV/AIDS prevention, (9) HIV testing, (10) living with HIV</p>	<p>(6) HIV and AIDS (1.02 minute) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=53kiDT7jUUw (7) HIV transmission (2.22 minute) https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s2-KbSyp838 (8) HIV/AIDS prevention (1.58 minute) https://youtu.be/RJy7vbYs1mU?feature=shared (9) HIV testing (1.04 minute)</p>	<p>Total time 7 minute</p>

		<p>https://youtu.be/gBYPtGFDQMs?feature=shared</p> <p>(10) living with HIV (1.14 minute)</p> <p>https://youtu.be/WzzdYCyE_70?feature=shared</p>	
<p>(11) information data for VCT and Deaf NGOs.</p>	<p>(11) information data for VCT and Deaf NGOs.</p>	<p>information data for VCT and Deaf NGOs</p>	<p>No estimation minute</p>